

Detailed description of pre-processing steps of the physiological data

A. Wrist Acceleration

The wrist acceleration data was cleaned with a 4th order bandpass filter with a low cutoff at 0.5 Hz and a high cutoff at 4 Hz. Then robust z -scores were calculated using the median and the median absolute deviation (MAD) of the whole data per participant. The root mean square (RMS) was subsequently calculated as a measure to combine the data of the movement axes x , y and z . The three movement axes and the calculated RMS values were used as metrics for the following analyses (TABLE I.).

B. Blood Volume Pulse (BVP)

Movement artefacts in the BVP data are removed with the help of the wrist acceleration data. The acceleration data was up-sampled to 64 Hz, denoised and RMS values were calculated. A cutoff value based on the sum of the mean and SD of the RMS values for each participant was calculated and raw BVP data points exceeding this cutoff were excluded. Monotone cubic spline interpolation was used to fill in the resulting missing values. The pyPPG package [1] was used for further data cleaning and the extraction of fiducial points and biomarkers from the BVP data. Peak-to-peak intervals between systolic peaks were then used to calculate the heart rate. Peaks were further filtered by ensuring that they represented heartbeats in the range of 40 – 180 bpm and that consecutive peaks do not change more than 20% [2]. Neurokit2 was utilized to further filter the peaks and to robustly standardize the data. From the final peaks, new peak-to-peak intervals and new heart rates were calculated. Neurokit2 was also used to calculate heart rate variability metrics in the time- and frequency domain (TABLE I.). The time-domain metrics comprise the mean (meanNN), median (medianNN) and median absolute deviation (madNN) between normal beat intervals (denoted as NN). Following deviation-based indices were considered: SDNN calculates the SD over the complete recorded section. SDNNI1, SDNNI2 and SDNNI5 are the SDNN indices that calculate the mean of the SD of NN calculated over one, two and five minutes respectively. Difference-based indices examine successive NN intervals. The root mean square of successive difference (RMSSD), the standard deviation of successive difference (SDSD) and the proportion of successive NN intervals that are larger than 20 ms (pNN20) or 50 ms (pNN50) are considered. Robust indices like the median absolute deviation of MCVNN (madNN/medianNN), the interquartile range (IQRNN) and the SDRMSSD (SDNN/RMSSD) are also included as metrics. The frequency-domain metrics that are included in this study are the low frequency (LF; 0.04 – 0.15 Hz), high frequency (HF; 0.15 - 0.4 Hz) and the ratio of low and high frequency (LFHF).

C. Electrodermal Activity (EDA)

A cutoff value based on the RMS values of the denoised down-sampled (4 Hz) acceleration data was used to remove large movement artefacts. Additionally, values below 0 were removed, since these values indicate no skin contact of the sensor [3]. Missing values were also interpolated using a monotone cubic spline interpolation. Further artefacts in the signal were filtered with a 2nd order high-pass Hamming filter (cutoff frequency $f = 0.05$ Hz) [4]. The signal was further smoothed with a moving average filter of four data

points, i.e. number of data points per second [4]. The robust z -scores were calculated (see above). The non-negative sparse deconvolution (sparsEDA) approach [5] was then used to decompose the EDA signal into its tonic and phasic components. Skin conductance responses (SCRs), represented as peaks in the phasic component of the signal, were detected when they crossed the threshold of minimal amplitude ($\text{amp} = 0.05$) [6], [7]. Metrics were then calculated from these signal components and from the frequency domain of the cleaned EDA signal (TABLE I.). The metrics are the accumulative EDA signal [8] and the mean and SD of the tonic component (skin conductance level (SCL)) (meanSCL, SDSCL). The phasic components (SCRs) were used for the metrics NumberPeaks/DurationSCR, which normalized the number of peaks with the duration of the task, the meanAmpSCR, which calculates the mean amplitude of the SCRs, meanRiseTimeSCR, which represents the mean time it takes for a SCR to reach maximal amplitude from onset and the meanRecoveryTimeSCR, which takes the mean of the SCRs to half recover from maximum amplitude. Posada-Quintero et al. [9] suggested to also consider the frequency domain of the EDA signal (0.045 – 0.25 Hz) which represents the dynamics of the sympathetic nervous system (Sympathetic). SympatheticN is obtained by normalizing the Sympathetic metric with the total power.

D. Skin Temperature

The same procedure as in the case of the EDA data was used to calculate the cutoff value. Temperature values which coincided with high movement were eliminated. Additionally, values below 25°C and above 40°C were eliminated [3], [10]. The missing values were interpolated using a monotone cubic spline. Further smaller movement artefacts were removed with a moving average window of one-minute windows. Robust z -scores were calculated to standardize the data and features were calculated. The mean skin temperature (meanTEMP), standard deviation (SDTEMP) and the range (rangeTEMP) were considered as metrics (TABLE I.).

TABLE I. FEATURE OVERVIEW OF THE DIFFERENT PHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS THAT WERE CALCULATED PER TASK PER PARTICIPANT.

Signal	Analysis category	Metric
BVP	Time-domain	Heart rate (HR) meanNN, medianNN, madNN, SDNN, SDNNI,1 SDNNI2, SDNNI5, RMSSD, SDSD, pNN20, pNN50, MCVNN, IQRNN, SDRMSSD
	Frequency-domain	LF, HF, LFHF
EDA	Tonic	EDA_Accumulative meanSCL, SDSCL
	Phasic	NumberPeaks/DurationSCR, meanAmpSCR, meanRiseTimeSCR, meanRecoveryTimeSCR
	Frequency-domain	Sympathetic, SympatheticN
TEMP		meanTEMP, SDTEMP, rangeTEMP
ACC		xMeanACC, yMeanACC, zMeanACC

Detailed result description for physiological measures

A. RQ2: Subjectively felt and objectively measured cognitive load

An overview of the physiological metrics that significantly correlate with the subjective cognitive load ratings from the cognitive load questionnaire is presented in TABLE II. According to Spearman's correlation coefficient, the subjective rated cognitive load correlates positively and significantly with the HRV features SDNNI1 ($p = 0.0285$), SDSD ($p = 0.0423$), IQRNN ($p = 0.0468$) and pNN20 ($p = 0.0114$) and highly significantly with pNN50 ($p = 0.0079$) from the BVP signal. In the case of the EDA signal, cognitive load ratings correlated significantly with NumberPeaks/DurationSCR ($p = 0.02$), SympatheticN ($p = 0.0376$) and highly significantly with EDA_Accumulative ($p = 0.0085$). The meanTEMP correlates significantly ($p = 0.0259$) and positively with the subjective experienced cognitive load. The RMS values calculated from the wrist acceleration data correlate highly significantly ($p < 0.0001$) with the subjective cognitive load ratings. High cognitive load correlates with low RMS values. One-sided permutation tests with random pairings and 9999 permutations were conducted per correlation to investigate the reliability of the small effect sizes. The significant results in TABLE II. indicate that the positive correlations of our study data are not the result of random pairing.

B. RQ3: Task differentiation

Some physiological features differ significantly between certain task categories. However, none of the features differs significantly between all three task categories. Details are given in TABLE III.

The following features of the BVP signal differ significantly between task categories: MadNN ($p = 0.028$), MCVNN ($p = 0.027$), SDRMSSD ($p = 0.032$), pNN50 ($p =$

0.026) and LFHF ($p = 0.035$) and highly significant for IQRNN ($p = 0.008$) and pNN20 ($p = 0.009$). Post-hoc tests on SDRMSSD, pNN50 and LFHF did not show significant results between specific task categories. Development-heavy activities and other activities differed significantly with higher mean values for development-heavy activities than for other activities in the case of MadNN ($p = 0.012$, $d = 0.736$), MCVNN ($p = 0.012$, $d = 0.733$) and highly significantly for IQRNN ($p = 0.0026$, $d = 0.883$). The pNN20 feature differed significantly between collaboration-heavy and other activities ($p = 0.042$, $d = 0.605$) and almost significantly between development-heavy and other activities ($p = 0.054$, $d = 0.578$).

The rise time of the SCR of the EDA signal differed significantly ($p = 0.0363$) between task categories according to Friedman's test. The post-hoc test revealed a significant difference between collaboration-heavy and other activities with longer rise time for other activities ($p = 0.04$, $r = 0.4978$).

The standardized mean skin temperature differs highly significantly ($p = 0.002$) between task categories. The post-hoc test shows that development-heavy and other activities differ highly significantly ($p = 0.0092$, $d = 0.758$) and collaboration-heavy and other activities differ almost significantly ($p = 0.0561$, $d = 0.525$). Skin temperature is highest for development-heavy activities.

The task categories also highly significantly differ ($p < 0.0001$) based on the RMS values of the acceleration data. Development-heavy and other activities differ highly significantly ($p < 0.0001$, $r = 0.9939$) and collaboration-heavy and other activities differ highly significantly ($p < 0.0001$, $r = 0.8648$). Acceleration is highest during other activities.

TABLE II. CORRELATIONS BETWEEN PHYSIOLOGICAL METRICS AND SUBJECTIVE COGNITIVE LOAD RATINGS

Physiological signal	Metric	Spearman's correlation coefficient	p-value	p-value _{permutation}
BVP	SDNNI1	0.1303	0.0285*	0.0282*
	SDSD	0.1173	0.0423*	0.0418*
	IQRNN	0.1351	0.0468*	0.0226*
	pNN20	0.1715	0.0114*	0.0054**
	pNN50	0.1798	0.0079**	0.0043**
EDA	EDA_Accumulative	0.162	0.0085**	0.0085**
	NumberPeaks/DurationSCR	0.1395	0.02*	0.0196*
	SympatheticN	0.1213	0.0376*	0.0395*
TEMP	meanTEMP	0.1322	0.0259*	0.0264*
ACC	RMS	-0.3571	<0.0001***	<0.0001***

TABLE III. THE PHYSIOLOGICAL METRICS THAT DIFFERED BETWEEN THE THREE TASK CATEGORIES DEVELOPMENT-HEAVY (D), COLLABORATION-HEAVY (C) AND OTHER ACTIVITIES (O) WERE ANALYZED VIA A ONE-WAY ANOVA OR THE NON-PARAMETRIC FRIEDMAN TEST

Physiological signal	Metric	ANOVA (F)	p-value	Mean (M _d)	Mean (M _c)	Mean (M _o)
		Friedman test (χ^2)		Median (MD _d)	Median (MD _c)	Median (MD _o)
BVP	MadNN	F(2,38) = 3.949	0.028*	M = 79.2	M = 76.6	M = 68.4
	MCVNN	F(2,38) = 3.98	0.027*	M = 0.0851	M = 0.0829	M = 0.0722
	SDRMSSD	F(2,38) = 3.761	0.032*	M = 0.873	M = 0.871	M = 0.902
	pNN20	F(2,38) = 5.414	0.009**	M = 29.7	M = 30.1	M = 26.0
	pNN50	F(2,38) = 4.009	0.026*	M = 22.6	M = 22.4	M = 20.4
	IQRNN	F(2,38) = 5.482	0.008**	M = 110	M = 104	M = 94
	LFHF	F(2,38) = 3.671	0.035*	M = 1.04	M = 1.04	M = 1.14
EDA	meanRise	$\chi^2(2) = 25$	0.0363*	MD = 1.97	MD = 1.86	MD = 2.05
	TimeSCR					
TEMP	meanTEMP	F(2,38) = 7.312	0.002*	M = 0.0389	M = -0.0597	M = -0.501
ACC	RMS	$\chi^2(2) = 21.9$	<0.0001* **	MD = 3.37	MD = 3.05	MD = 5.39

REFERENCES

- [1] M. Á. Goda, P. H. Charlton, and J. A. Behar, "pyPPG: a Python toolbox for comprehensive photoplethysmography signal analysis," *Physiol Meas*, vol. 45, no. 4, p. 045001, Apr. 2024, doi: 10.1088/1361-6579/ad33a2.
- [2] A. Muaremi, B. Arnrich, and G. Tröster, "Towards Measuring Stress with Smartphones and Wearable Devices During Workday and Sleep," *Bionanoscience*, vol. 3, no. 2, pp. 172–183, Jun. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s12668-013-0089-2.
- [3] S. Böttcher et al., "Data quality evaluation in wearable monitoring," *Sci Rep*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 21412, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.1038/s41598-022-25949-x.
- [4] B. Choi, H. Jebelli, and S. Lee, "Feasibility analysis of electrodermal activity (EDA) acquired from wearable sensors to assess construction workers' perceived risk," *Saf Sci*, vol. 115, pp. 110–120, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.ssci.2019.01.022.
- [5] F. Hernando-Gallego, D. Luengo, and A. Artes-Rodríguez, "Feature Extraction of Galvanic Skin Responses by Nonnegative Sparse Deconvolution," *IEEE J Biomed Health Inform*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 1385–1394, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1109/JBHI.2017.2780252.
- [6] H. F. Posada-Quintero and K. H. Chon, "Innovations in electrodermal activity data collection and signal processing: A systematic review," *Sensors*, vol. 20, no. 2, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.3390/s20020479.
- [7] Society for Psychophysiological Research Ad Hoc Committee on Electrodermal Measures, "Publication recommendations for electrodermal measurements," *Psychophysiology*, vol. 49, no. 8, pp. 1017–1034, Aug. 2012, doi: 10.1111/j.1469-8986.2012.01384.x.
- [8] N. Nourbakhsh, F. Chen, Y. Wang, and R. A. Calvo, "Detecting users' cognitive load by galvanic skin response with affective interference," *ACM Trans Interact Intell Syst*, vol. 7, no. 3, Sep. 2017, doi: 10.1145/2960413.
- [9] H. F. Posada-Quintero, J. P. Florian, A. D. Orjuela-Cañón, T. Aljama-Corrales, S. Charleston-Villalobos, and K. H. Chon, "Power Spectral Density Analysis of Electrodermal Activity for Sympathetic Function Assessment," *Ann Biomed Eng*, vol. 44, no. 10, pp. 3124–3135, Oct. 2016, doi: 10.1007/s10439-016-1606-6.
- [10] I. R. Kleckner et al., "Simple, Transparent, and Flexible Automated Quality Assessment Procedures for Ambulatory Electrodermal Activity Data," *IEEE Trans Biomed Eng*, vol. 65, no. 7, pp. 1460–1467, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1109/TBME.2017.2758643.